

THE INSCRIPTION ON THE PIPRĀWĀ VASE.

The Piprāwā inscription, so ably treated by Dr. Fleet in the January number (pp. 149 sqq.), exhibits one rather interesting feature, which seems to have hitherto escaped observation, namely, that it is composed in metre, forming a somewhat irregular rhyming Āryā verse.¹

īyāṃ sā|lilānī|dhānō || būdhās|a bhāgāvā|tē sū|kiyā|na(m) |
sūkīṭī|bhātī|nā(m) sābhāgī|nikā|nā(m) sāpū|tā|dālā|na(m) ||

Both lines have an unusual amphibrachys in the first foot, and the second by its imperfect caesura seems to deserve the title *Vipulā*. It may be noted that the metre is almost decisive in favour of the reading *sābhaginikāna(m)*, with the second *i* long. The fact that the inscription is in metre may affect the consideration of interpretations based on order, and as regards the meaning of *sūkīṭī* I am inclined to ask whether Bühler's original understanding of it as an ordinary proper name has been justifiably abandoned in favour of the application to Buddha, which seems to lack testimony. The name *Sukīrti* occurs in the *Mahāvastu*, vol. i, p. 136, l. 14.

However, Professor Pischel's *Sukīṭī* in the sense of 'pious foundation' (*Zeitschrift d. deutschmorgentl. Gesellschaft*, 1902, pp. 157-8) would be from the point of view of metre equally acceptable.

The irregularities in the scansion of the verse will not prove too much for the credence of those who will consult the Āryā verses occurring in the *Therāgāthā*, pp. 162, sqq. (Pali Text Society, 1883). In these, first noted by Professor Jacobi, as I learn from Professor Pischel, who has edited the text strictly in accordance with the MSS., we find exemplified not only *-ām*, *-ē*, and *-ō*, but also amphibrachys in the first and third foot, etc.

¹ The marks of quantity relate to the syllable, not to the vowel. *tē sū|kiyā|naṃ* | is a suggestion of Professor Rapsou.

[Dr. Fleet points out that the verse may preferably be regarded as an *Upagīti*, in which case I am inclined to agree with him that the first word of the inscription is *Sukīti*—

Sūkitī|bhātī|nā(ṃ) sābhāgī|nikū|nā(ṃ) sūpū|tā|dālā|na(ṃ) |
īyāṃ sā|lilānī|dhānē || būdhā|sā bhāgāvū|tē | sākīyū|na(ṃ) ||

Possibly the last word might be scanned *sākīyā|na(ṃ)*.

I have previously (in this Journal, 1903, pp. 831–3) pointed to some apparent verses in the inscriptions of Aśoka, and suggested that others would hereafter be discovered. The following inscription now seems to me to be metrical:—

Gīhīlēnā | Sihārā|khītēnā cā || bhātūrē|hī Tākhāsī|lāē |
āyāṃ thū|vō prātī|thāvītō || sārva|bū|dhānā pū|yāē ||

(*Peshawar Vase.*)

Here we seem to have a rhyming verse consisting of five feet of five *mātrās* with a concluding spondee; but I am not acquainted with the metre elsewhere.

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THE SAKYAS AND KAPILAVASTU.

I venture to call attention to two points in Mr. Fleet's paper on the inscription on the Piprāwā vase.

In tracing the origin of the tribal name Śākya through the forms Śākīya, Sākīya, śākīya, to the word śāka, he has taken this last word in the sense of 'a teak-tree' (p. 163 above); and that is in accordance with the dictionaries.

But the application of the word śāka in Northern India is to the *sāl*-tree (*Shorea robusta*); and the teak-tree is called *sāgwān*. It may be that the latter word has led the interpreters astray. Anyhow, the *sāl*-tree is also called *sāku* throughout the districts and provinces bordering on Nepal, and a tract of *sāl*-forest is called *sākuwan* or *sakuwan*. As *sāl* represents *śāla*, *sāku*, *saku*, will represent *śāku*. The teak is not indigenous to the Nepal Terai forests. They are essentially *sāl*-forests, and Śākya obviously means 'the people of the *sāl*-forest tracts.'